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Co-design as a key element in the creation of inclusive and sustainable urban spaces in vulnerable environments

The New European Bauhaus approach in the neighbourhood of Las Palmeras, Córdoba

The European research project H2020 IN-HABIT (<https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu>) aims to investigate how the integration of social, cultural, infrastructural and digital innovations can increase health and well-being in small and medium-sized cities in the periphery of Europe, especially in vulnerable neighbourhoods and groups, working with a participatory, gender and inclusive approach.

The project, coordinated by the University of Cordoba, is being developed in 4 European cities: Cordoba, Lucca (Italy), Riga (Latvia) and Nitra (Slovakia), and it examines how the links between elements such as culture, art, heritage, relationships with nature and animals, or healthy eating, act as promoters of health and well-being in the urban contexts of the EU periphery, favouring the transition towards more liveable, sustainable and human cities. In each

of these cities, we created the so-called IN-HUB, a platform for social interaction between all those institutions, associations, companies, citizens, etc. who are interested in participating in the project or being linked more or less informally to its actions.

In Cordoba, the project explores the relationship between key elements such as culture (understood as a physical element and an inherent part of human beings, resulting from their experiences and their relationship and interaction with the environment) and tangible and intangible heritage, and health and well-being, and the influence of other elements such as vulnerability, gender, or inclusion.

An important part of IN-HABIT's activities in Cordoba is carried out in the Las Palmeras

neighbourhood, where different types of innovative actions have been implemented since September 2020 to study how they affect the health and well-being of its inhabitants. This neighbourhood is considered one of the 15 most vulnerable neighbourhoods in Spain, being the sixth neighbourhood with the lowest per capita income in Spain (INE, Urban Indicators 2019), as well as having a high unemployment rate and a high rate of absenteeism from school, leading to dropout and failure. This situation is aggravated by a high rate of informal economy and illegal activities.

IN-HABIT's actions aim at the social transformation of the neighbourhood by creating accessible, green, aesthetic and inclusive spaces through social and cultural innovations that boost the co-creation and appropriation of these spaces by the inhabitants. To this end, all the actions carried out have involved social and community participation, seeking to generate social capital through co-design, co-implementation and co-evaluation strategies.

The project's actions are perfectly in line with the principles of the New European Bauhaus: sustainability, beauty and community, as its principles are inclusion, sustainability and aesthetics. Here we present the main elements of the co-design methodology implemented in the neighbourhood and its contributions to the NEB, in order to promote its replicability in other contexts.

Our working method is organised around the following 3 phases:

- 1. Knowing the reality:** In-depth analysis of the situation in the neighbourhood using various tools: guided and informal interviews with neighbours, participatory observation, focus groups, mapping of actors and contacts with public, private and NGO institutions in order to initiate processes of social change.
- 2. Working together to create aesthetic, inclusive and sustainable spaces:** Creation of a driving group that brings together the main associations and organisations working in Palmeras, carrying out co-design workshops with neighbours, joint implementation of actions to create urban spaces that incorporate elements of aesthetic, in-

Situación original de la Plaza central del barrio de Las Palmeras y estado actual tras la intervención.

clusive and sustainable beauty, as well as creating synergies with organisations present in the rest of the city.

- 3. Valorisation of results:** Co-evaluation of results and identification of elements of replicability of actions that can contribute to the NEB. Establishing a working dynamic between the neighborhood and the city of Cordoba.

During the first phase, diagnostic work was carried out, and different working dynamics were established. This allowed the second phase to design, together with the district's neighbours, a series of actions aimed at improving the quality of life of its inhabitants through innovative actions promoting sustainability, inclusiveness, accessibility, and access to culture.

El barrio de Las Palmeras está considerado entre los 15 barrios más vulnerables de España, siendo el sexto de los barrios con menor renta per cápita de España

En Córdoba, el proyecto está estudiando la vinculación de elementos claves como la cultura y el patrimonio con la salud y el bienestar, además de cómo interactúan con otros elementos como la vulnerabilidad, el género o la inclusión

The aim was not only to carry out physical actions in the urban space but also to promote processes of social transformation linked to changes in the urban space. In the third phase, the results will be co-evaluated with the neighbours, as well as with the different entities and individuals involved in IN-HABIT, through the aforementioned IN-HUB, which functions as a laboratory for social action and innovation, in order to identify lessons and good practices, as well as opportunities for improvement.

So far, two of the main actions have been

- **The transformation of the central square of the neighbourhood into a meeting place.** Through various co-design workshops and with the support of the neighbours, school students, members of different organisations, and other stakeholders, the Plaza de la Concordia, as it is known in the neighbourhood, has been restored as a meeting place for the people, and where various celebrations have been held (Christmas parties, carnival, May crosses...). The square has been renovated and embellished with the participation of the residents and the work of businesses in the neighbourhood, making it visible as a space for all and made by all. This has initiated a process of social change that has not yet been consolidated but is in progress (see photos).
- **The transformation of the southern plot of the Cantarranas stream into a neighbourhood picnic area.** Again, through co-design workshops with a group of neighbours committed to improving health and well-being, an abandoned and degraded space has been rehabilitated, creating a picnic area that

Limpieza, construcción y acto de inauguración del merendero.

INCLUSIVE HEALTH AND WELLBEING IN SMALL AND MEDIUM SIZE CITIES (IN-HABIT)

Este proyecto se desarrolla en cuatro ciudades europeas (Lucca, Italia; Riga, Letonia; Nitra, Eslovaquia, y Córdoba, España) pero lo coordina la Universidad de Córdoba. Hay un consorcio de más de 27 miembros de más de seis países. El proyecto también está vinculado con la ciudad de Bogotá (Colombia).

DURACIÓN

01/09/2020 - 31/08/2025.

PRESUPUESTO

Coste total 11.577.918,75 euros (aporte de la UE: 10.501.931,25 euros).

ÁREAS DE INTERVENCIÓN

Se trabajan cinco líneas:

- Renaturalización y medioambiente
- Cultura, arte y patrimonio
- Infraestructura, tecnología y digitalización
- Salud y bienestar
- Género, diversidad, inclusión e innovación.

CIFRAS DE IMPACTO

Alcance del proyecto en Córdoba desde 2020 hasta diciembre de 2023:

+1.200

participantes en estudios y encuestas.

+1.800

participantes en acciones en actividades culturales y de hábitos de vida saludable.

+1.200 m²

de espacios verdes creados.

+5.353 m²

de espacios recuperados.

+70

talleres realizados.

+20

empleos directos e indirectos creados.

+8

eventos culturales y de promoción de hábitos de vida saludable.

has become a green meeting place in the neighbourhood, appreciated and cared for by the neighbours. In this way, the tradition of meeting around the Cantarranas stream, which dates back to the neighbourhood's origins but was abandoned due to the space's unhealthy conditions and the administration's neglect, has been recovered (see photos).

The main factors that can make these actions replicable and contribute to the development of NEB principles in other actions are:

- 1. Approaching the social reality of the neighborhood from multiple perspectives:** IN-HABIT has made a great effort to get to know and work with the main protagonists: the different social groups and the different associations and institutions present in the neighborhood. The actions are based on the commitment of neighbors, associations and institutions, thanks to the creation of a driving group and reinforcing their role as a community platform that brings together the different sensitivities of the neighborhood.
- 2. Accompanying and strengthening the community** as a fundamental pillar of the actions, i.e. empowering the inhabitants as the main stakeholders and active actors in their own transformation process, taking into account all their contributions, and reaching consensus on the final actions through inclusion and co-design.
- 3. Adapting to the community's needs,** workshops open to the neighbours allowed the community to participate in solving its problems, trying to see these problems as opportunities and challenges rather than as a barrier to its development and growth (co-implementation).
- 4. Using and claiming the right to neighborhood spaces** as links between people, and fostering a sense of belonging and healthy coexistence through accessible, inclusive and beautiful neighborhood spaces.
- 5. Progressing towards an urban transformation that improves health and well-being:** The project is based on the firm commitment of the neighbours and neighbourhood entities

to move forward in an urban transformation that increases health and well-being through actions of social transformation. Thus, we can already see results in terms of neighbourhood empowerment, ownership of actions, greater sense of identity and de-stigmatisation, among others.

- 6. Engaging other institutions and entities of Cordoba** present in the IN-HUB, together with the funding and the IN-HABIT team, allows the development of the actions requested by the neighbours in the participatory workshops, the amplification of them and the creation of links and synergies that strengthen the project's sustainability.
- 7. Dissemination capacity and visibility of an international project:** European projects have a high capacity to attract attention at different levels. The novelty of the issues addressed and the need to promote inclusive health and well-being in cities has allowed the results of IN-HABIT to be communicated in local, regional, national and international forums.

All these aspects strengthen the sustainability and replicability of the actions. The project aims to identify a set of good practices in urban and social development to achieve more inclusive, sustainable, healthy, environmental and nature-friendly cities that incorporate distinctive elements such as beauty, community participation and sustainable recovery of public spaces. IN-HABIT was designed and approved before the NEB, but its approach perfectly aligns with this initiative's principles.

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SABER+

<https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu>